

AICON
2024

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

**Compliance of supply and demand on specialty in the context of the
personalization of education**

Ph.D.Huseyn Gasimov
Nakhchivan State University
hqasimov@gmail.com
ORCID ID:0000-0002-3714-875X

Abstract:

In the conditions of the labor market, which is diversifying day by day and the demands are changing in a fuzzy way, the traditional form of education in universities is losing its relevance. In this case, the concepts of "personalization of education" and "individual education trajectory" are more prominent. The components of both concepts are the knowledge and skills of the student, the requirements for knowledge and skills of the majors, the duration of education, vacancies, etc. in itself is observed with complex fuzzy situations.

In order to ensure the competitiveness of future graduates in the context of the changing labor market, the article deals with the issue of matching the supply and demand for specialties in the context of personalization of education.

In order to ensure the matching of supply and demand for specialties, first of all, the situational models of supply and demand for learners were described, occupations and applicant clusters and demand matrices for each cluster were prepared. The process of placement of applicants by specialty is presented in the form of two sets of fuzzy situations describing the situations of demands and offers.

At the next stage, in order to evaluate the degree of similarity of an arbitrary real situation with the corresponding standard situation for the solution of the decision-making issue, degrees of fuzzy inclusion and equivalence of two fuzzy situations were presented.

As a result of the process of recognizing more suitable pairs according to the degree of similarity of the "specialization - learner" pair in the set of real images of learners and standard images of the survey, several possible scenarios and realization of decision-making issues were presented in stages.

As a result, the proposed method is one of the support methods for making more informed decisions by matching supply and demand in the process of placing learners in e-universities in order to prepare more quality personnel for the knowledge economy society.

Introduction

Demands that are enhanced day by day in the labor market lead to the rapid changes in the need for the staff. In this case, it may be more appropriate to organize short-term qualification courses in accordance with the current requirements of the society rather than predicting the qualifications to be required in next 4-5 years. Given the diversity and

multiplicity of the demands for the qualified cadres and the skills offered in the labor market, which forms and operates under uncertainty, the application of intellectual methods and technologies for adapting these indicators can provide more effective results. This, in turn, necessitates the issue of personalization of education. From this point of view, first of all, supply and demand for the learners to be trained through at e-university [3] environment through the individual education trajectories should be adapted. In this regard, the labor market should be viewed as an indefinite intellectual environment [4]. In this case, the habits, skills and initial knowledge are taken as the basis to achieve the result [1,2].

Situation model of supply and demand for learners

If the professions trained at e-university are conditionally denoted by "P", then the demands for professions can be described as follows:

$P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d\}$ or $P = \{P_b\}, b = \overline{1, d}$ denote a set of professions;

$V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_y\}$ or $V = \{v_z\}, z = \overline{1, y}$ is a set of personal characteristics that must have a learner, i.e., the candidate to be trained on the profession; $F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_r\}$ or $F = \{f_o\}, o = \overline{1, r}$ is a set of competences that must have the candidate ambitious for the profession; $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_x\}$ or $E = \{e_t\}, t = \overline{1, x}$ is the initial knowledge that the applicant should have on separate subjects and topics.

Thus, the demand model $P = (V, F, E)$ for each profession is represented by three matrices: $P_V = \|v_{bz}\|_{dy}, P_F = \|f_{bo}\|_{dr}, P_E = \|e_{bt}\|_{dx}$. Here, each row $b = \overline{1, d}$ of P_b characterizes the separate professions provided by e-university, and the columns (v_{dy}, f_{dr}, e_{dx}) represents the ever-expanding base of personal characteristics, competences and initial knowledge. The elements v_{dy}, f_{dr} are the level of individual indicators required to be trained in a particular profession, e_{dx} is the level of knowledge on separate subjects required for a specific profession. Compliance of the student's knowledge with the specialty is determined by the neural network. The provision of the indicators v_{dy}, f_{dr} and e_{dx} of the profession $P_b (b = \overline{1, d})$ is determined by the following fuzzy set membership function:

$$\mu_{v_{bz}}(P_b): P \times V \rightarrow [0,1], \mu_{f_{bo}}(P_b): P \times C \rightarrow [0,1], \mu_{e_{bt}}(P_b): P \times E \rightarrow [0,1] \quad (1)$$

and represents the membership rate required by e-university on selected professions for separate indicators.

If the applicants eligible for any specialty of e-university are denoted by "A", then a set of applicants will be conditionally shown as $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_s\}$ or $A = \{A_h\}, h = \overline{1, s}$. Thus, $V = \{v_z\}, z = \overline{1, y}$ is a set of personal features of the applicant who wants to study on the specialty, $F = \{f_o\}, o = \overline{1, r}$ is a set of open competences of the applicant on the specialty, and

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

$E = \{e_t\}, t = \overline{1, x}$ is a set of indicators of initial knowledge level of the learner on separate subjects and topics.

In this case, the supply model $A = (V, F, E)$ is also represented by three matrices: $A_V = \|v_{hz}\|_{sy}, A_F = \|f_{ho}\|_{sr}, A_E = \|e_{ht}\|_{sx}$. Here, each row $h = \overline{1, s}$ of A_h describes separate applicants on selected specialty, while the columns (v_y, f_r, e_x) represents the constantly expanding database of personal features, competences and initial knowledge of applicants. The elements V_{hy}, f_{hr} denote the possession rate of indicators that the applicants should have to be trained on specific occupation, whereas e_{hx} is the level of knowledge required for specific subjects. The possession rate of the specific student A_h in the personal features $(h = \overline{1, s})$ V , competence F and knowledge E on subjects is determined by the following membership function:

$$\mu_{v_{hz}}(A_h): A \times V \rightarrow [0,1], \mu_{f_{ho}}(A_h): A \times C \rightarrow [0,1], \mu_{e_{ht}}(A_h): A \times E \rightarrow [0,1] \quad (2)$$

The process of applicants' placement on the specialties is a set of two fuzzy situations describing the situation of demand $\tilde{P}_b$ and supply $\tilde{A}_h$:

$$\tilde{P}_b = \{ \langle \mu_{v_{bz}}(P_b) \rangle, \langle \mu_{f_{bo}}(P_b) \rangle, \langle \mu_{e_{bt}}(P_b) \rangle \} = \{ \mu_{P_b}(y) / y \} \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{A}_h = \{ \langle \mu_{v_{hz}}(A_h) \rangle, \langle \mu_{f_{ho}}(A_h) \rangle, \langle \mu_{e_{ht}}(A_h) \rangle \} = \{ \mu_{A_h}(y) / y \} \quad (4)$$

Here, $\tilde{P}_b = \{ \mu_{P_b}(y) / y \}, b = \overline{1, d}$ are the fuzzy reference situations or sought fuzzy images of demand required by e-university on specialties, while $\tilde{A}_h = \{ \mu_{A_h}(y) / y \}, h = \overline{1, s}$ is a set of real situations that the applicant experienced, that is, the sought fuzzy images of supply.

Recognition of fuzzy images of supply and demand for learners

Accordingly, the statement and goal of the decision-making issues related to the compliance of supply and demand is to determine the similarity of two fuzzy situations and to manage the situations using the proximity metrics. The determination of the degree of fuzzy inclusion of fuzzy situation $\tilde{A}_h$ to the fuzzy situation $\tilde{P}_b$ and the determination of the degree of fuzzy equation $\tilde{A}_h$ and $\tilde{P}_b$ may be used as the evaluation method of similarity between the random real situation and the corresponding reference situation; [2]:

1. The degree of fuzzy inclusion $\theta(\tilde{A}_h, \tilde{P}_b)$ of fuzzy situation $\tilde{A}_h$ to the fuzzy situation $\tilde{P}_b$ is defined as follows:

$$\theta(\tilde{A}_h, \tilde{P}_b) = \&\theta(\mu_{A_h}(y), \mu_{P_b}(y)) = \&_{y \in Y} (\max(1 - \mu_{A_h}(y), \mu_{P_b}(y))) = \min(\max(1 - \mu_{A_h}(y), \mu_{P_b}(y))) \quad (5)$$

If the degree of fuzzy inclusion of fuzzy situation $\tilde{A}_h$ to the fuzzy situation $\tilde{P}_b$ is not less than the fuzzy inclusion limit ψ accepted according to the management

requirement, that is $\theta(\tilde{A}_h, \tilde{P}_b) \geq \psi$, then, situation $\tilde{A}_h$ is fuzzy included to the situation $\tilde{P}_b$, that is $(\tilde{A}_h \subseteq \tilde{P}_b)$. More precisely, if the fuzzy value of the indicators of the situation $\tilde{A}_h$ are fuzzy included to the value of the indicator of the situation $\tilde{P}_b$, then, the situation $\tilde{A}_h$ is fuzzy included to the situation $\tilde{P}_b$.

For decision making, each alternative situation from the set of specialties, which the learner applied to, is compared with the degree of inclusion of the specialty (the specialties from the set of specialties) to the reference images. According to the following expression, the most compatible specialty is selected as the search result:

$$\max[\min(\max(1 - \mu A_h(y), \mu P_b(y)))]_{h = \overline{1, s}, b = \overline{1, d}}$$

2. The degree of fuzzy equivalence as the metrics of the similarity degree the two random fuzzy situations is defined as follows. Assume that the fuzzy equivalence limit ψ of the two situations is defined, and if there are situations that are mutually included into each other, that is $\tilde{A}_h \subseteq \tilde{P}_b$ and $\tilde{P}_b \subseteq \tilde{A}_h, h = \overline{1, s}, b = \overline{1, d}, h \neq b$, then, the situations $\tilde{A}_h$ and $\tilde{P}_b$ are considered to be approximately equal. The degree of similarity, called fuzzy equation of situations, is calculated based on the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(\tilde{A}_h, \tilde{P}_b) &= \vee(\tilde{A}_h, \tilde{P}_b) \vee(\tilde{P}_b, \tilde{A}_h) = \& \mu(\mu A_h(y), \mu P_b(y)) = \\ &= \min_{y \in Y} [\min(\max(1 - \mu A_h(y), \mu P_b(y)), \max(\mu A_h(y), 1 - \mu P_b(y)))] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

If $\mu(\tilde{A}_h, \tilde{P}_b) \geq \psi$ when they are included into the assigned limit ψ , and then the situations $\tilde{A}_h$ and $\tilde{P}_b$ are considered to be fuzzy equal, that is, $\tilde{A}_h \approx \tilde{P}_b$.

Management methods of compliance of supply and demand for learners on possible scenarios

As a result of the process of recognition of more compatible pairs "specialty - learner" according to their similarity degree in the set of the real images of learners and the reference survey images, several possible scenarios may be revealed:

1. One learner (student) claims to study on one specialty.

In this case, the decision is made related to the compliance of the learner with the specialty, if the fuzzy similarity degree of the two situations (the reference image of the specialty and the real image of the learner) is not less than the limit assigned by e-university.

2. Several learners claim to study on one specialty according to the similarity degree of two fuzzy situations. In this case, the learners generate a sub-set of fuzzy alternatives out of which the most compatible applicants should be chosen.

In this case, e-university may make decision in the process of placement of the applicants by the specialties following the methods proposed below:

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

2.1. The similarity degrees of reference and real situations are compared by the criteria characterizing the applicants who are eligible for specialties, and decisions related to the most compatible situations are made.

2.2. Decision-making is brought to the multicriteria selection issue to select better alternatives, taking into account the relative importance factors of the criteria characterizing the applicants.

In this case, the decision-making process is performed on the stages proposed below:

At the first stage the situations that do not provide the fuzzy inclusion or equivalence limit are “eliminated”, i.e., the corresponding applicants do not take part at the next stage.

At the second stage, the relative importance coefficients of criteria and indicators are determined [6]. In this regard, Saaty table and a comparison matrix is set in accordance with the diagonal, symmetrical and transitiveness features of the matrix. The relative importance coefficients are calculated using one of the four approaches proposed in [6].

The maximum specific value λ_{max} of the matrix and the Consistency Index (CI)- and the Consistency ratio (CR) are calculated to verify whether the expressions of the e-university, which represent pair comparison of indicators, contradict or not, and to detect these contradictions. Based on the method of multiplying the matrix by vector, a rough estimation of consistency is used [6]. By multiplying the comparison matrix by the obtained decision vector (relative importance ratios), a new vector is obtained. Consequently, dividing the first component of obtained vector by the first component of the decision vector, and respectively, the second component by the second component of the decision vector, and so on, a further vector is obtained. λ_{max} (maximum or key specific value) is obtained by the division of the sum of the components of this vector by the total number of components. The closer the value of λ_{max} to n , the more the issue is deemed to be agreed. Deviation from the consistency is called the Consistency Index (CI) and this limit is defined by formula:

$$CI = (\lambda_{max} - n) / (n - 1) \quad (7).$$

The division of the consistency index of the matrix by the Random Consistency (RC) allows defining Consistency Relation (CR):

$$CR = CI / RC \quad (8)$$

According to [7], for $n = 3$, Random Consistency is $RC = 0,58$; for $n = 4$, Random Consistency is $RC = 0,90$; for $n = 5$, Random Consistency is $RC = 1,12$; for $n = 6$, Random Consistency is $RC = 1,24$, and so on. If $CR \leq 0,1$, consistency limit is considered to be acceptable, otherwise, the values of reference images should be viewed again.

At the third stage, the fuzzy similarity degree of the fuzzy real situation with the reference situation is defined based on the aggregation of indicators. This is performed in the following steps.

3.1. By setting the "wrap" of the indicators $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_y$, the fuzzy similarity degree of the fuzzy real situations $A = \{A_h\}, h = \overline{1, s}$ with the fuzzy reference situations $P = \{P_b\}, b = \overline{1, d}$ in accordance with V is determined:

$$\mu_V(A_h) = \sum_{z=1}^y w_z \mu_{v_z}(A_h). \quad (9)$$

3.2. By setting the "wrap" of the indicators $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_r$, the fuzzy similarity degree of the fuzzy real situations $A = \{A_h\}, h = \overline{1, s}$ with the fuzzy reference situations $P = \{P_b\}, b = \overline{1, d}$ in accordance with F is determined:

$$\mu_F(A_h) = \sum_{o=1}^r w_o \mu_{f_o}(A_h). \quad (10)$$

3.3. By setting the "wrap" of the indicators $e_1, e_2, \dots, e_x$, the fuzzy similarity degree of the fuzzy real situations $A = \{A_h\}, h = \overline{1, s}$ with the fuzzy reference situations $P = \{P_b\}, b = \overline{1, d}$ in accordance with E is determined:

$$\mu_E(A_h) = \sum_{i=1}^x w_i \mu_{e_i}(A_h). \quad (11)$$

3.4. Based on the results obtained and the relative importance ratios w_v, w_f, w_u of the criteria W, F, E , the similarity degree of fuzzy real situations with the reference situations are defined:

$$\mu_p(A_h) = \omega_V \cdot \mu_V(A_h) + \omega_F \cdot \mu_F(A_h) + \omega_E \cdot \mu_E(A_h) \quad (12)$$

3.5. The fuzzy real situation with the highest value is selected:

$$\mu(A^*) = \max\{\mu_d(A_b), b = \overline{1, y}\} \quad (13)$$

The selected fuzzy real situation is the sought image of the applicant with the highest degree of similarity and can be considered as the best decision.

Conclusion

The method proposed in this paper is one of the decision support methods for the training of high-quality cadres for the knowledge-based economy in the process of placement of learners at e-universities through the compliance of supply and demand. This issue can be solved through: verbal analysis of results [7] and decision methods in fuzzy conditions [8], considering the importance and insignificance of indicators on occupational qualifications [9]; bringing to collective decision making [10]; bringing to the issue of multi-criteria decision-making taking into account the combination of different conditions [5]. The dynamics of the individual characteristics required for each specialty, diversity of specialization, distribution of qualified personnel in different areas,

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən praktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

belonging to different age categories and other similar factors may be considered as the main condition of support.

References

1. Zadeh L.A. The concept of a linguistic variable and its application to the approximate decision making, Moscow: Mir, 1976, 168 p.
 2. Mammadova M.G., Decision making based on knowledge base with fuzzy relational structure, Baku: ELM, 1997, 296 p. (Mamedova M.G. Prinyatie reshenij na osnove baz znaniy s nechetkoj relyacionnoj strukturoj. - Baku, Elm, 1997)
 3. M.H. Mammadova, H.A. Gasimov, “E-university: conceptual, technological and architectural approaches”, Problems of information technology, 2017, no. 2, pp. 51–62. DOI: 10.25045/jpit.v08.i2.06
 4. M.H. Mammadova, Z.G. Jabrayilova, F.R. Mammadzada. [Managing the IT labor market in conditions of fuzzy information](https://link.springer.com/article/10.3103/S0146411615020030) // Automatic Control and Computer Sciences, 2015, vol.49, no.2, pp.88-93 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.3103/S0146411615020030>
 5. M.H. Mammadova, F.R. Mammadzadeh, “Formation of supply and demand for IT Specialists on the base of competency model”, Proc. of the IV IEEE International Conference Problems of Cybernetics and Informatics (PCI-2012), 2012, sept.12-14, Baku, 2012, vol.IV, pp. 199–201. www.pci2012.science.az/8/12.pdf
 6. Saaty T.L. Making decisions. The method of analyzing hierarchies, M.: Radio and communication, 1993, 320 p.
 7. Larichev O.I. Verbal analysis of decisions. M.: Nauka, 2006, 181 p.
 8. Bellman R., Zadeh L.A. Decision- making in fuzzy environment // Management Science, 1970, vol.17, pp.141–164.
- Mammadova M.H., Jabrayilova Z.Q., Mammadzada F.R. Fuzzy Multi-scenario Approach to Decision-Making Support in Human Resource Management. In book: L.A. Zadeh et al. (eds.), Recent Developments and New Direction in Soft-Computing Foundations and Applications, Studies in Fuzziness and Soft Computing, Springer International Publishing Switzerland 2016, vol.342, pp.19–36. DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-32229-2_3